

study design undergoes a peer-review process before data is gathered. Early feedback and transparency help improve methodological rigor, and in many cases, this feedback also comes with a commitment to publish the study regardless of its results. On the one hand, this discourages practices like HARKing (hypothesizing after results are known), which can compromise the validity of findings. On the other, it encourages the publication of negative results, which are often undervalued but critical to advancing knowledge in the field. Not being pressured to produce positive outcomes to secure publication, researchers are more likely to uphold the scientific imperative of disinterestedness.

By publishing our research design ahead of data collection, we act on our motivation to strive for a more open and trustworthy research culture in empirical software engineering. This report can therefore also be understood as a commitment to publish outcomes independent of their implications for prior work.

Due to the double-blind review process of the conference this work was submitted to, we do not reference the online publication of the present report. The online publication will be added to the manuscript only after the review process.

II. METHOD

Prior exploratory work investigated testing experiences using qualitative research strategies. Swillus and Zaidman [6] analyze documents to uncover the roots of sentimental attitudes of developers towards testing. Following that, Swillus, Hoda, and Zaidman [10] analyzed semi-structured interviews to explore the topic further. We choose a survey-based study design to extend this line of work on socio-technical aspects of software testing. In the following sections, we describe how we construct the survey instrument. We follow Kitchenham and Pfleeger [17], which provides a guideline to create personal opinion surveys. The rest of this section is organized according to the six activities Kitchenham et al. identify in their guideline. As this report is published prior to data collection, we only consider the first four activities, which lead to the construction of a survey instrument and a preliminary plan for its evaluation.

- Setting the objective
- Survey Design
- Developing the survey instrument
- Evaluating the survey instrument

III. SETTING THE OBJECTIVE

Declaring the research objective, including the hoped-for outcomes, is necessary to constrain the scope of questions in a survey [18]. To identify the research objective, we choose a top-down approach [19, p.10], breaking down the broader research question we want to tackle into concrete hypotheses based on prior work.

A. Research Questions

We argue that the many factors influencing developers' engagement with testing often lead to unanticipated outcomes, which can understandably provoke emotions. We align with Rooksby, Rouncefield, and Sommerville [20] who describe testing as a stochastic process: What makes a test plan effective is often the ability to handle various unpredictable contingencies as they arise. Swillus, Hoda, and Zaidman [10] identify factors that can give rise to these contingencies, and others that enable developers to manage them. The objective of this study is to further investigate the interplay of those factors:

- RQ1** How does the interplay of testing conditions shape a software developer's motivation to use testing?
RQ2 How does the interplay of testing conditions shape a software developer's perception of the value of testing?

Prior work observed that concrete conditions influence how testing is perceived and used, as well as which factors encourage developers to reflect on their testing practices [10]. While prior work has identified conditions related to developers' motivation to test, it has yet to determine whether there are common patterns or combinations that stimulate or inhibit testing. A key goal of this work is to identify these relationships and examine how they correlate with testing usage and motivation.

- RQ3** Which sets of conditions are common among developers who are motivated to engage in testing?

To investigate this question, we aim to measure developers' motivation regarding software testing, their self-reported perception of effort spent on testing, and their evaluation of how conditions such as *testing infrastructure*, *complexity*, or a developer's *autonomy* impact their efforts.

IV. SURVEY DESIGN

Swillus, Hoda, and Zaidman [10] investigate the socio-technical context of software testing through qualitative methods, identifying conditions that shape how testing strategies emerge in practice. While that work surfaces rich descriptions of developer experience, its propositions have not been tested quantitatively. The present work addresses this by operationalizing key constructs into a survey instrument. By making testing experience measurable, we aim to enable future work to identify which combinations of conditions are most conducive to testing engagement. We follow Kitchenham and Pfleeger [17] in constructing a personal opinion survey, as this method is particularly suited to investigating factors rooted in the perspectives of practitioners. Theoretical propositions from Swillus, Hoda, and Zaidman [10] are broken down into concrete hypotheses, and further into measurable constructs and survey items.

We construct a descriptive cross-sectional survey to discover factors and their impact on practice at one fixed point in time. The survey therefore provides a snapshot of what developers experience. We implement the survey using a web-based self-administered questionnaire, as this format facilitates simple distribution and coverage of the population we want to study.

Each hypothesis is operationalized as a set of measurable constructs. For example, the hypothesis "*the presence of usable testing infrastructure increases the motivation to test*" contains two constructs: testing infrastructure and motivation. In the context of this study, testing infrastructure refers to software and operational systems that support developers in their testing activities, like existing test suites or CI/CD systems. Accordingly we operationalize testing infrastructure by measuring the usability of software testing tools available to developers. However, measuring motivation in questionnaires is considered a non-trivial task [21]. Following Touré-Tillery and Fishbach [22] who differentiate between multiple dimensions of motivation, we consider two measurable aspects of motivation: goal-focused motivation, which reflects an outcome-oriented attitude, and process-focused motivation, which reflects an intrinsic attitude of *doing it right*. Each construct is measured through a dedicated set of survey items.

Before approaching the implementation of the survey instrument, we conduct a lean literature review to determine how others have investigated the factors we want to measure. Re-using tested and peer-reviewed instruments increases the credibility and reproducibility of results.

V. LEAN LITERATURE REVIEW

By reviewing available literature, we establish to what extent the construction of a new instrument is required. Re-using tested and peer-reviewed instruments increases the credibility and reproducibility of results. We also familiarize ourselves with approaches others have chosen to investigate similar phenomena, in order to learn how the many aspects of it can be observed, conceptualized, and measured. Identifying measurable variables through this process is the first step in constructing survey questions. The aim of a lean literature review is not to provide a comprehensive overview of all relevant topics, but rather to scan and scope, optimized to serve its key aims quickly and as easily as possible [23, p.119].

1) *Motivation*: Motivation of software developers has already been researched for over 40 years, as it has been identified as an important factor impacting software developer productivity. Questionnaires are often used to measure various aspects that relate to motivation [24]. Over the years, many different motivators that affect developers, including recognition, trust, autonomy, and variety of work, have been identified [24], [25]. Different models of motivation of software developers have been proposed [21], and though many different perspectives on motivation have been researched, it remains a complex topic. As the world is changing, past work on motivation needs re-validation to remain insightful. Unfortunately this is done very little [21]. A more recent study by Verner, Babar, Cerpa, *et al.* [26] about motivation using survey instruments finds that social factors and human needs are important for developer motivation. Developers seem to be motivated by a project manager with good communication skills, in projects where risk is controlled, when the work environment is supportive. In their survey, Verner, Babar, Cerpa, *et al.* [26] measure motivation by asking developers in a self-administered online questionnaire about the motivation of their team members. Similar to Daka and Fraser who asking participants directly: "What motivates you to write unit tests?" [27]. Straubinger *et al.*, who investigate opinions of software developers regarding testing, take a different approach because they identify that *motivation* is an overloaded term [28]. Motivation, they argue, is a multi-dimensional concept which needs to be considered from many angles in order to be analysed. They do not directly ask developers about their motivation but instead ask about circumstances of their work that transcend motivation. Aligning with this view, social psychologists consider motivation to be a construct that cannot be recorded or observed directly. Accordingly, measuring motivation in experiments or through questionnaires is considered a non-trivial task. In a guideline to measure motivation, Touré-Tillery *et al.* suggest differentiating between outcome-focused motivation to complete a goal, and process-focused motivation (more commonly known as intrinsic motivation), which has less emphasis on the outcome and includes elements such as appropriate means and enjoyment during goal pursuit [22]. The first resembles an attitude of *getting it done*, the latter of *doing it right*. In experiments, indicators for those two aspects can be measured using different means. For example, outcome-focused motivation can be revealed through a subject's positive evaluation of goal-congruent constructs such as means, objects, or persons, and a subject's negative evaluation of goal-unrelated constructs such as distractions. Process-focused motivation is, in this context, revealed by positive evaluation of the process [22].

2) *Human factors and software development processes*: Several recent studies investigate how human and social factors influence software development practices and the organization of software development projects. Investigating success factors of agile method adoption using a survey instrument, Misra *et al.* find that technical competency, team size, and planning are not strong factors, but that corporate culture and training initiatives have a significant effect [29]. Instead of measuring success factors like *Corporate culture* using with questions, each success factor was measured using a set of questions that collectively represent the factor. Dybå uses a similar approach in a questionnaire-based study investigating the impact of company size on software process improvement [30]. According to their study, the size of companies in which software is developed influences how well projects can leverage different kinds of knowledge and expertise. To investigate influences on software process improvement, Dybå identifies six key success factors and breaks each factor down into several indicators, each measured using one question. The approach is motivated by the argument that complex concepts like software process improvement success factors can not be reliably measured through simple one-dimensional questions. Instead of measuring a factor with one question, multiple questions are therefore combined to measure each concept [30]. A similar approach is taken by Machuca-Villegas *et al.*, who investigate the perception of human factors that influence the productivity of software development teams [31]. In their survey instrument, they first consider key human factors and then scrutinize each using several questions [32]. Using the perspective of human factors, they find a positive influence of empathy, social interaction, communication, and autonomy on productivity.

3) *Software testing: Opinions and needs of developers*: In an attempt to close a gap between academic and practitioner views on software testing, Rafi *et al.* use a combination of a systematic literature review and a practitioner survey to investigate benefits and limitations of software testing practices [3]. Using their literature review, they derive a set of hypotheses which they test by asking practitioners whether they agree or disagree. As the studies considered in their review mostly focus on technical aspects, the results of their study also primarily concern technical aspects of software testing. For example, their survey demonstrates that the benefits of test automation are related to test reusability, repeatability, test coverage, and effort saved in test execution [3]. Daka and Fraser [27] also investigate testing practices with a focus on established practices and problems. They identify that there is a need to improve the technical capabilities of unit testing, especially in terms of automation. However, they also find that the need for testing is often motivated organizationally, and that a developer's own conviction is a strong factor. Like Rafi *et al.* [3], Daka and Fraser [27] measure aspects with distinct questions, but to increase the validity of those questions, they use verification questions (questions that measure the same variable using alternate wording). They then disregard responses where answers to the same question diverge. All questions were derived from their research questions, but how exactly those questions were developed is not clearly explained [27].

VI. HYPOTHESES AND VARIABLES

Swillus, Hoda, and Zaidman [10] identify eleven conditions that affect developers' testing practices:

- Complexity
- Software Development Process
- Safety & Responsibility
- Vision
- Resource Usage

- Mandates
- Testing Infrastructure
- Testing Culture
- Community Perspective
- Personal Leanings

A theory proposed in [10] conceptualizes software testing as a dualism, composed of ephemeral and material elements that influence each other. To approach **RQ1-3**, we focus our investigation on the interplay of a subset of above-mentioned conditions. First, we investigate how organizational conditions relate to developers' motivation to use testing practices and the extent to which testing is used in projects. Second, we explore the relationship between complexity and testing infrastructure in relation to testing motivation. Third, we examine how material and ephemeral aspects of testing influence one another.

1) *Software Process and Testing Motivation*: The introduction or adaptation of software testing methods within an organization can be seen as part of an effort to improve the software development process. Dybå [30] identified that the success of process improvement efforts depends on the correlation of particular organizational factors, including company size. Large companies benefit from structured processes that leverage past knowledge, while smaller organizations benefit more from experimentation and exploration [30]. Prior research suggests that business context and software development organization influence testing practices as well [10], [20]. Autonomy (reflected in the capacity to experiment) and the exploitation of existing knowledge appear to play major roles. Based on these findings, we propose the following hypotheses about the relationship between autonomy, knowledge sharing, and company size in the context of testing:

- [H1]** Organizational factors affect testing practices
- H1.1** In large companies, testing is used more extensively when past knowledge is extensively leveraged
 - H1.2** In small companies, testing is used more extensively when exploratory approaches are embraced
- [H2]** Motivation to test stems mainly from individual conviction and not from organizational factors. However, organizational factors do impact the extent to which testing is used.
- H2.1** Motivation to test is not significantly influenced by organizational factors such as mandates or company size
 - H2.2** The extent of testing is influenced by organizational factors such as mandates and company size

Testing these hypotheses requires measuring the following variables, for some of which measurement methods are described in the literature we reviewed in Section V:

- Company size (H1)
- Employee participation [14] and Mandates (H2)
- Extent of testing (H1)
- Exploitation of existing knowledge [14] (H2)
- Exploration of new knowledge [14] (H2)
- Motivation (process-focused and goal-focused) [22] (H2)

2) *Complexity and Testing Infrastructure*: The complexity of a software system can influence testing motivation in several ways. When software consists of multiple interacting components, systematic testing can help developers maintain an overview of the project. Testing becomes a way to reduce perceived complexity. However, complexity can also discourage testing if simple approaches are inadequate and the effort required for effective testing becomes overwhelming [6]. We argue that the availability of testing infrastructure and team culture significantly mediate this relationship:

- [H3]** The presence of usable testing infrastructure increases the process-focused motivation to test
- [H4]** The (perceived) complexity of a project impacts motivation to test
- H4.1** Complexity increases motivation if testing infrastructure is present
 - H4.2** Complexity decreases motivation if testing infrastructure is absent

Testing these hypotheses requires measuring the following variables, for some of which measurement methods are described in the literature we reviewed in Section V:

- Testing infrastructure (H3, H4)
- Motivation (process-focused and goal-focused) [22] (H3, H4)
- Complexity (H4)

3) *Material and Social Construction of Testing*: Swillus, Hoda, and Zaidman [10] conceptualize software testing as an interplay between material elements (e.g., test frameworks, source code, documentation) and ephemeral elements (e.g., discussions, culture). Developers leave *signatures* in code that reflect their testing values, while discussions and team culture produce *echoes* that foster testing culture. Testing-signatures can be understood as traces in artifacts (e.g., testing infrastructure) that represent developers' knowledge and experience and can spark reflection when encountered. We argue that the presence of this record of experience and knowledge can, when properly exploited by an organization stimulate discussions and reflections on testing.

Testing-echoes are collaborative reflections, of ideas and knowledge in the context of testing. We argue that this collaborative exploration of new ideas and a positive testing culture leads to the extension of testing efforts. In this context, we argue that it is the process of reflection that motivates developers to extend their testing efforts.

We further hypothesize that ambitions to extend testing practices benefit from autonomy, meaning the developer has influence on how the development process is structured.

- [H5]** Knowledge exploration positively influences the extent of testing efforts
- H5.1** A capacity to explore influences the extent of testing
 - H5.2** Active discussion and interaction influences the extent of testing
 - H5.3** Active discussion and interaction influences the impact of the capacity to explore on the extent of testing
- [H6]** Knowledge exploitation positively influences the extent to which testing practices are reflected
- H6.1** Knowledge exploitation impacts the extent of testing
 - H6.2** The presence of testing infrastructure influences the extent of reflection on testing
- [H7]** When testing practices are discussed interactively, motivation is higher and adoption of testing practices is greater
- [H8]** Whether reflection through testing echoes leads to code changes depends on the participant's level of autonomy

Testing these hypotheses requires measuring the following variables, for some of which measurement methods are described in the literature we reviewed in Section V:

- Exploration of new knowledge [14] (H5)
- Extent of testing (H5, H7)

- Discussion and interaction (H5, H6, H8)
- Exploitation of existing knowledge [14] (H6)
- Testing infrastructure (H6)
- Motivation (goal-focused) [22] (H7)
- Employee participation [14] and Mandates (H8)

4) *Summary*: We aim to illuminate relationships between organizational, technical, social, and cultural factors that shape software testing practices. The survey instrument we construct to investigate these relationships is designed to deepen our understanding of how and why developers are motivated to adopt testing, while also providing actionable insights to enhance testing processes across diverse development environments. In order to reach our research objective we measure 10 variables:

- 1) Company size, team size and testing mandates (H1)
- 2) Extent of testing (H1, H5, H7)
- 3) Complexity (H4)
- 4) Testing infrastructure (H3, H4, H6)
- 5) Discussion and interaction (H5, H6, H8)
- 6) Employee participation [14] and Mandates (H2, H8)
- 7) Exploitation of existing knowledge [14] (H2, H6)
- 8) Exploration of new knowledge [14] (H2, H5)
- 9) Motivation (process-focused and goal-focused) [22] (H2, H3, H4, H7)

Using a questionnaire to measure those variables we test eight hypotheses and aim to generate insights that enable more effective integration of testing strategies, ensuring that tools and techniques align with developers' needs, goals, and the broader organizational contexts in which they are employed.

VII. IMPLEMENTATION

For the 11 variables we want to measure with a questionnaire, we re-use three key factors of software process improvement in organizations from Dybå [14]. Dyba's questions are adapted where needed to fit our focus on software testing. To measure motivation, we use indicators for process-focused and goal-focused motivation as suggested by [22]. To measure goal-focused motivation we construct 5 questions which address the recall and evaluation of goal-related constructs that relate to testing. To measure process-focused motivation we construct 3 questions which address the evaluation of the impact of testing on the process of software development.

Further, we measure company size and team size with single-item questions. For company size, a range from a set of fixed values can be selected (<50; 50-250; >250). Values for team size are selected from fixed values as well (1 (solo project); 2-4; 5-7; 8-10; 11 and more). We also measure the presence of a testing mandate through a single-item question that is answered with a standard 5 point likert scale: "*Testing is strictly required when contributing to the software I develop*".

Both Swillus, Hoda, and Zaidman [10] and the literature reviewed above indicate that the remaining variables we want to measure are inherently complex and multi-faceted. To reliably measure complex variables, we therefore follow an approach similar to [14]. Instead of using a single question to measure the four remaining, complex variables we use multi-item scales which measure a single variable with multiple representative indicators. The scores (in this context called *scale scores*) of each variable are then calculated through the sum of all respective indicators. For each factor we want to measure, we therefore construct three or more indicators. For each indicator we then construct one question. For example, to measure *complexity*, one indicator is a developers' *perception of technical complexity of the project*. From this indicator, we derive the following statement, which is answered using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly

agree to strongly disagree: *I consider the software project as complex: it is large and consists of many components which interact with each other*. We choose 5-point Likert scales with the same options for all questions in our survey instrument, except for demographic questions. Table I contains all factors and corresponding questions.

TABLE I: Multi-scale variables and corresponding questions. Questions in column 3 were developed and refined after the indicators in column 2 were derived from the hypotheses discussed in Section VI. Indicators marked with a dagger (†) were deleted after instrument validation and not used during data analysis. Indicators marked with a double dagger (‡) were added after the pilot phase due to feedback from participants.

Variable	Indicator	Question
Extent of Testing	Extent to which testing is used as an individual activity to develop software	I am making extensive use of software testing techniques in my daily software development activities
	Extent to which testing is used by the project to develop software	The project for which I develop software is making extensive use of software testing
	The organization supports and embraces software testing	The organization in which the project is embedded promotes the usage of software testing practices
Mandate	Degree to which testing is mandated	Testing is strictly required when contributing to the software I develop
Complexity	Perception of technical complexity of project	The software project I contribute to is large and consists of many components which interact with each other
	† Usage of standard tools	We mainly use common, standardized technologies when we develop, test, build and distribute the software we develop
	† Degree to which best practices can be used	Large parts of the code base use common patters that can be learned in books or online.
	‡‡ Multi-disciplinary nature of project	Software development requires collaboration across disciplines (e.g, DevOps, data science)
Infrastructure	Extent of tool support for testing goals	Our project is built upon strong testing frameworks which include elements like test suites and development tools
	Ability to use testing with respect to resources available	I (would) have enough time to expand and improve our project's testing framework
	† Importance of existing source code for the extensions of test suites	I often reuse existing source code when developing new tests
	Extent of explicit guidelines for testing in the project	Guidelines and expectations for testing are clearly defined and explicitly documented
Discussion and Interaction	† Degree to which discussions translate to contributions	Conversations about testing usually lead to actual improvements in our testing efforts
	Degree to which testing is learned through mentoring	I learned a lot about testing through colleagues who taught me how to approach it
	Extent of implicit guidelines for testing in the project	I mainly know what is expected of me in terms of testing by interacting and talking with other developers
	† Extent to which testing culture can establish something as untestable	There is a shared understanding in our project that parts of the software we develop are untestable
	† Extent to which testing culture influences the perceived difficulty of testing in project	In our team testing tasks are considered to be straight forward and easily done
Employee Participation	† Extent of employee involvement in decisions that should best be done at their own level	Software developers are involved to a great extent in decisions about the implementation of their work
	Extent to which employees contribute with improvement proposals	Software developers are actively contributing with proposals to adapt testing strategies
	Extent of developer participation in the formalization of routines	Software developers are actively involved in creating routines and procedures for testing
	† Extent of ongoing dialog and discussion about software development	We have an on-going dialogue and discussion about software development
	Extent of ongoing dialog and discussion about software testing	We have an on-going dialogue and discussion about software testing
Exploitation of Existing Knowledge	Extent to which existing knowledge is exploited	We exploit the existing organizational knowledge to the utmost extent
	Extent of learning from past experiences	We are systematically learning from the experience with prior projects
	† Degree to which formal routines are based on past experience	Our routines for software testing are based on experience from prior projects
	† Degree of systematization of past experience	We collect and classify experience from prior projects
	Degree of internal experience transfer	We put great emphasis on internal transfer of positive and negative experience

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Variable	Indicator	Question
Exploration of New Knowledge	Degree of adaptability to rapid change, increasing complexity and environmental uncertainty	We are very capable at managing uncertainty in the organization's environment
	Extent to which innovation/change is encouraged	In our organization, we encourage innovation and creativity
Motivation (goal-focused)	Degree of experimentation with new ideas, strategies and technologies	We often carry out trials with new software engineering methods and tools
	Degree of experimentation with new ideas, strategies and technologies	We often conduct experiments with new ways of working with software development methods.
	† Ability to question underlying values	We have the ability to question <i>established</i> truths
	† Degree of flexibility in task execution	We are very flexible in the way we carry out our work
	† Degree of detail in task specification	We do not specify work processes more than what is absolutely necessary
	† Importance of matching the variety and complexity of the organization's environment	We make the most of the diversity and interests to manage the variety and complexity of the organizations environment
	† Extent to which testing is perceived to contribute to software quality goals	Software testing practices enable developers to write better code
	Degree of accessibility and memory for goal-congruent constructs (means, objects, person)	I can name several testing tools and methods that (would) help me to achieve the project's goals
	Degree of accessibility and memory for goal-incongruent constructs (temptations)	I can recall many situations in which testing related work distracts me from getting the job done
	† Degree of positive evaluation of goal-congruent constructs (means, objects, persons)	Testing tools, methods and testing contributions of my colleagues are crucial for the success of our project
Motivation (process-focused)	Degree of negative evaluation of goal-incongruent constructions (temptations, distractions)	Unnecessary testing tasks often distract me and hinder my progress towards my actual goals
	Extent to which software testing contributes to pr.	Software testing increases my productivity
	Positive experience from the process	I enjoy using software development more when I use software testing tools and practices
	Positive evaluation of the process	The use of software testing methods and tools positively impacts my workflow
		End of table

Score	Answer Criteria
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not relevant so it should be removed • This item is not clear • This item has no logical relationship with the factor. • This item can be removed without affecting the factor measurement
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It must be rewritten • The item requires several modifications or a very large modification in terms of wording or structure • A very specific modification is required for some wording • The item has a moderate relationship with the factor it is measuring • The item is relatively important
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This item is relevant • This item is clear with proper semantics and syntax • This item is completely related to the factor being measured • This item is very relevant and must be included

TABLE II: Item assessment criteria for survey instrument evaluation

VIII. EVALUATING THE SURVEY INSTRUMENT

Before turning the instrument into a web-based questionnaire that can be self-administered by participants, all questions and answers should be evaluated. Evaluation serves multiple goals[17]

- Ensure that questions are understandable
- Assess the likely response rate
- Determine the reliability and validity of the instrument
- Test the data analysis techniques on expected outcomes

To evaluate the survey instrument we first conduct an unstructured interview with a software developer who we consider to be an expert on the topic. After the interview in which we discuss the research objective we incorporate the interviewee’s feedback into the first draft of our questionnaire and then give our questionnaire to the interviewee for a more structured evaluation. We ask them to rate each question on a scale from one to three, ranging from *Not relevant - should be removed* to *relevant - can remain as is* and provide explanations for each answer in free text fields. We provide an extensive description of each point on the evaluation scale, which we take from the work of Machuca-Villegas et al. [32] and can be seen in Table II.

After we incorporate this in-depth feedback, we conduct a pilot study for which we recruit a small group of software developers to complete the questionnaire and encourage them to provide feedback about questions using free-text fields. Through feedback from the pilot study we further improve wording and clarity where possible. We also use the data gathered in the pilot study to run preliminary tests for reliability and validity.

IX. INSTRUMENT VALIDATION

We validate the survey instrument after data collection. We use multi-item scales, which measure a single complex variable by combining the measurements of multiple indicators for most variables of our survey. In order to verify that the questions we use in our survey consistently measure what they are supposed to measure and to evaluate how each question contributes to the respective scale, we use tests for reliability, and content-, construct-, and criterion validity.

A. Reliability Score

We perform a consistency and stability analysis for each multi-scale variable used in our survey. Internal consistency of a construct can be tested with the coefficient alpha [33]. The coefficient alpha expresses how homogeneous items in a scale are. Values vary between 0 and 1. The more reliable all items measure the same concept the closer the coefficient alpha approaches 1. We follow recommendations by Eisinga, Grotenhuis, and Pelzer [34], and calculate the

TABLE III: Reliability scores for each construct after we remove questions with negative effect on reliability

	Alpha	Questions	Removed Q.
Extent Testing	0.750	3	None
Motivation Process	0.840	3	None
Motivation Goal	0.710	3	2
Complexity	0.380	3	1
Infrastructure	0.730	3	1
Interaction	0.650	3	2
Knowledge Exploration	0.760	8	None
Knowledge Exploitation	0.830	5	None
Employee Participation	0.810	5	None

standardized Cronbach-alpha, also called *Spearman-Brown prediction* for groups of two items. The coefficient alpha can be regarded as a lower bound of reliability [35], scores above 0.7 are sufficient for narrow constructs in the early stages of instrument research [33], scores between 0.55 and 0.7 for broad constructs respectively [36]. Table III shows the coefficient alpha for each factor. We consider the removal of items if their removal substantially increases the coefficient alpha of the respective factor and thereby increases the consistency of the scale. We also consider the removal in terms of its content-level impact on the construct.

- Items 1 and 4 of the Goal Motivation scale were removed. Both have a low correlation with the overall scale and demonstrate a low coefficient alpha.
- We remove Item 4 of the Complexity scale, which was added after the pilot to complement the Complexity scale, because its removal increases the coefficient alpha of the scale by more than 0.2 points.
- We remove Item 3 of the Infrastructure scale because its removal increases not only the coefficient alpha of its scale but also has a positive impact on all further validity tests. This indicates that Item 3 does not measure the quality or availability of infrastructure (which we intended to measure). Instead it might measure the style of software testing a participant practices (copying existing tests instead of starting from scratch).
- Interaction 4 and 5 demonstrate a low coefficient alpha suggesting that they measure a different concept than intended. Item 5 aims to measure the extent to which testing culture influences the perceived difficulty of testing in projects. This indicator is measured by asking whether testing tasks are considered to be straightforward and easily done by the team. Similarly, Item 4 aims to measure the extent to which testing culture can render a project as untestable. It is possible that the emphasis on shared understanding of difficulty was not evident enough in the questions. Without this emphasis, both items are more likely to measure the perceived difficulty of testing on an individual level. We therefore remove both items.

B. Correlation Scores

Next, we perform a *corrected item-scale correlation analysis* [37] to identify how each item contributes to the scales we constructed. We correlate each question with each scale, excluding the question from the scale to which we originally assigned it. For each item in Table IV we determine whether it should be removed or reassigned to a better-fitting factor. Items listed warrant evaluation because their correlation with the assigned factor is weak (below 0.3), or because they correlate more strongly (difference of at least 0.2) with a factor they were not originally assigned to. For cases of weak correlation, we check whether removal would eliminate an essential dimension

TABLE IV: Issues to resolve after corrected correlation analysis. The table shows all items for which the correlation score (r) is lower than 0.5. The last row indicates the action we took to improve the underlying construct.

	r	Better	Solution
Motivation G. 2	0.320	None	
Complexity 1	0.060	None	Remove
Complexity 2	0.290	None	Remove
Complexity 3	0.330	None	
Interaction 1	0.270	Exploitation: 0.5	Re-assigning
Exploration 7	0.250	None	Remove
Exploration 8	0.440	None	

from the respective scale. For cases with a stronger correlation with another factor, we evaluate whether reassignment is appropriate. The last column in Table IV indicates how we resolved each case.

Even though we deleted 2 items from the Interaction scale already, Item 1 of the same scale still shows a weak correlation. The item is however correlated with factor *Knowledge Exploitation*. Item *Interaction 1* is supposed to indicate the degree to which discussions about testing translate to contributions. The question reads: “Conversations about testing usually lead to actual improvements in our testing efforts”. The item was originally supposed to measure the effect of interaction on the production of actual testing infrastructure. The stronger correlation with the concept of *Knowledge Exploitation* however suggests that it actually measures the degree to which the potential of interaction can be leveraged. We therefore re-assign the item. Further, multiple items do not reach the correlation threshold of 0.3. We therefore consider their removal.

- Item 7 in Knowledge Exploration demonstrates a low correlation with its scale. We argue that the wording of the question, mentioning ‘software process’ could be too ambiguous and that it instead measures the perceived autonomy of a developer at their workplace in general.
- Item 8 in the same scale also demonstrates a low correlation with the scale. Similar to Item 7 we hypothesize that the question was too ambiguous. One person provides feedback in the open question section of the scale, mentioning that they do not understand the item.
- We re-assign the first item in the Interaction scale to the Knowledge Exploitation scale. The question asks whether communication leads to actual changes. It may imply to participants that existing knowledge is put into practice which matches the concept of exploitation of existing knowledge better than Interaction.

C. Factor Analysis

Next, we carry out a principal component analysis. With a principal component analysis we measure the extent to which each item measures the same construct. Assuming that a scale is valid, we use the result of this analysis as an indicator for the construct validity of the scale.

We consider three criteria: First, we evaluate the eigenvalue of each scale [38]. An eigenvalue larger than 1 indicates that the scale explains more variance than the average amount of variance explained by one item. Second, we use a scree test to determine which factors can be omitted [39]. Last, we inspect the factor loadings for component 1 of the factor analysis of each scale, and consider items below 0.45 for removal. Values above 0.45 indicate a fair loading [40]. Table V shows eigenvalues (λ) and the loading range for component 1 of the factor analysis. As a result of this analysis we

TABLE V: Results of factor analysis for each multi-item construct. Values correspond to eigenvalues and factor loadings for the first component of the factor analysis.

	λ	Loading Range	Loading > .45
Extent Testing	2.11	0.52 to 0.63	3 of 3
Motivation Process	2.30	0.54 to 0.62	3 of 3
Motivation Goal	1.88	0.41 to 0.66	2 of 3
Complexity	1.37	0.09 to 0.71	2 of 3
Infrastructure	1.93	0.53 to 0.61	3 of 3
Interaction	2.00	0.18 to 0.64	2 of 5
Knowledge Exploration	3.15	0.28 to 0.45	1 of 8
Knowledge Exploitation	3.18	0.4 to 0.49	2 of 5
Employee Participation	3.09	0.39 to 0.5	3 of 5

remove the following questions: Knowledge Exploration 5 & 6 and Knowledge Exploitation 3 & 4 were removed because the eigenvalue in the scree-plot indicates low importance for the respective factor. We remove Interaction 1 from Knowledge Exploitation, to which it was re-assigned in the last step, too. The factor loading of Interaction 1 was below the threshold we define above. A scree plot for the eigenvalues of each scale can be found in the online analysis tool of our replication package [41].

D. Final set of questions

After we systematically validate each scale above, issues remain with the multi-item score that measures complexity. First, the second item in the scale (“Common, standardized technologies are used to develop, test, build and distribute the software” correlates with question of the same scale (“Large parts of the code base use common patterns that can be learned in books or online.”) but not with the first question of the scale, which we consider to be essential for this variable (“The software project is large and consists of many components which interact with each other”). We therefore decide to remove both, the second and third item of the scale and only keep item 1, turning complexity into a single-item scale.

E. Interactive online repository

All steps of instrument validation are also documented online, through an interactive website. We refer the reader to <https://replication.alumncloud.net> where they can find additional graphs and statistics. The source code of the application can be found in the replication package [41] and may be re-used under the terms of Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.

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